

The Role of Roughness-Induced Damping in the Oscillatory Motion of Bilayer Graphene

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Abstract. A multi-scale theoretical model is presented that is the first to offer quantitative agreement with experimental measurements of self-retraction and oscillation of bilayer graphene. The model integrates density-functional calculations of the energetics driving flake retraction and molecular-dynamics simulations capturing the dynamic response of laterally-offset rough surfaces. We demonstrate that nanoscale roughness explains self-retraction motion and propose a recipe for tuning that motion by controlling friction.

1. Introduction

Graphene has many novel properties and characteristics that make it a promising material for a variety of applications [1]. Recently, multilayer graphene was found to exhibit an exciting new behavior where the uppermost layer, after being laterally offset from those below it, retracts to its initial position [2, 3, 4, 5], sometimes after oscillating [6]. The physics behind this behavior can be understood easily in terms of energetics: the offset position is energetically unstable, so the upper layer moves towards the overlapping, low energy position [2, 5, 6, 7, 8, 10]. The dynamics of the motion are then determined by factors that affect the energy gradient, including commensurability [8, 10] and temperature [2]. Theoretical approaches that capture these effects can reproduce experimentally-observed trends [6, 9, 10], but have not, to this point, predicted self-retraction or oscillatory behavior that is quantitatively comparable to experimental measurements. One reason for this is that prior modeling studies have not included surface roughness and the corresponding effect on the rate at which oscillations are damped. Here, we directly address this issue, thereby enabling a more complete understanding of self-retraction motion.

In this work, molecular dynamics (MD) simulations that explicitly capture graphene surface roughness are carried out. In addition, density functional theory (DFT) calculations are performed to verify that the energetics of the empirical model-based MD simulation are accurate. Finally, a reduced-order model is presented that captures both the energetics of the DFT and the roughness-dependent dynamic response of the MD. Model predictions are compared directly to previous experimental results and highlight the important role of roughness in determining motion patterns. Ultimately, since the roughness of graphene can be controlled to some extent by the substrate material and morphology, this work suggests a means of tuning self-retraction or oscillation motion of layered materials.

2. Methods

The model used in the DFT calculations was two parallel hydrogen-terminated flakes with 58 carbon atoms each (lower right inset of Figure 1). We used the LC- ω PBE-XDM functional [16, 17, 18] with the 6-31G* basis set as implemented in Gaussian09 [19]. The flakes were displaced parallel to each other, optimizing the inter-flake distance at each point.

The MD simulations consisted of two square graphene flakes (lower left inset of Figure 1) with side lengths between 5 and 20 nm where the top flake was initially offset relative to the bottom by a distance L in the armchair direction. The atoms at the two ends of the flakes in the offset direction were treated as rigid bodies. The root-mean-square (R_q) roughness was varied from 0 to 0.7 Å by changing the relative distance between the two ends of the graphene and then allowing the system to relax. The further the two ends of the graphene were compressed, the rougher the final

Figure 1. Variation in the potential energy with offset position, illustrating the V-shaped profile that drives the system towards its low-energy overlapped configuration as well as local variation due to the atomic structure of the graphene. The lower insets are snapshots of the MD (left) and DFT (right) models. The side length and offset are defined in the upper inset.

configuration (Figure S-1 in the supplemental information illustrates the relationship between compression distance and R_q). Model roughnesses were comparable to the range of values measured experimentally for graphene on a boron nitride substrate (0.02-0.17 Å)[11]. The inter-atomic interactions within the graphene flakes were described via the Adaptive Intermolecular Reactive Empirical Bond Order (AIREBO) potential [14], and the long range interactions between them modeled using the Lennard-Jones potential (energy minimum 0.016 eV, zero-crossing distance 2.8 Å). The accuracy of the potential was validated by comparing the interlayer interaction energy obtained by energy minimization with the empirical potential to that calculated using DFT; the comparison illustrating good agreement between the two methods is shown in Figure S-2 of the supplemental information. A Langevin thermostat was applied to the free atoms in the system to maintain a temperature of 300K and simulations were performed using LAMMPS [15].

3. Results and Discussion

Despite the difference in size between the MD and DFT model graphene flakes, the energy per unit area predicted by MD and DFT can be overlaid and show good agreement, as seen in Figure 1. The potentials both have a characteristic V-shape, exhibiting greater stability at maximum overlap, where the dispersion energy will be largest in magnitude [9, 6]. The linear dependence of the energy on the offset implies a constant interaction energy per overlapping area. The potential also has superimposed oscillations due to the periodicity of the graphene lattice [9, 6]. This allows us to introduce a simple one-dimensional model for the potential energy of interaction between two graphene flakes, where the equations of motion can be solved directly [2].

Consider a system of two identical graphene flakes, each with length L_0 , width W_0 and area $A_0 = L_0 \times W_0$. The displacement between the centers-of-mass of the flakes (offset) is L and we define a dimensionless displacement or mismatch ratio as $x = L/L_0$. The potential has a characteristic V-shape, with a superimposed sinusoidal oscillation. This can be written as

$$E = k_1 A_0 |x| - k_2 A_0 (1 - |x|) \cos\left(\frac{2\pi L_0 x}{p}\right). \quad (1)$$

In this expression, k_1 is the energy density per contact area between the two flakes (discussed later), the period $p = 4.267 \text{ \AA}$ is the distance between the centers of adjacent carbon-rings in the armchair direction, and $k_2 = 0.00015 \text{ eV/\AA}^2$ was calculated from the amplitude of the oscillatory energy profile that results from subtracting a V-shaped curve from the MD potential energy vs. mismatch ratio data (see Figures S-3 and S-4 in the supporting information). We have found that this parameter is roughly constant and independent of the size of the flakes.

We obtain k_1 by linear regression of the MD-predicted energy vs. offset x data, which gives $0.011697 \text{ eV/\AA}^2$. The value of k_1 determined from the LC-wPBE-XDM calculations on the 5x4-cell double flake is $0.011826 \text{ eV/\AA}^2$. k_1 also can be estimated from equivalent DFT-XDM calculations under periodic boundary conditions by displacing two infinite graphene slabs relative to each other and calculating the binding energy with respect to the isolated slabs. These calculations were performed using the PW86[21]PBE[22]-XDM[23] functional, implemented in the Quantum ESPRESSO program[24]. Although this approach is expected to be less accurate than LC-wPBE-XDM, it enables us to incorporate periodic boundaries, comparable to the MD simulation. Using this method, k_1 was estimated to be 0.01886 eV/\AA^2 at the energy minimum and 0.01545 eV/\AA^2 at the maximum by dividing the binding energy by the unit-cell area. We note that all these values are similar to those obtained experimentally for the interlayer binding energy of highly-oriented pyrolytic graphite, $0.011875 \text{ eV/\AA}^2$. Hence, k_1 is a constant in a range that spans a 5x4-cell double flake ($\sim 1\text{nm}$ range), our MD simulations ($\sim 10\text{nm}$), experiment ($\sim 2\mu\text{m}$), and infinite contact areas. Model predictions shown next are obtained using $k_1 = 0.0118 \text{ eV/\AA}^2$.

The force on the flake is then

$$F = -\frac{dE}{dx} \frac{1}{L_0} + cL_0 \frac{dx}{dt} \quad (2)$$

where the first term is the conservative force coming from the potential energy and the second term is dissipative and captures the effect of friction. Similar to previous formulations, the friction force is proportional to the sliding velocity [2]. Its magnitude is determined by the variable coefficient c , which will be related to the surface roughness. The equation of motion to be solved is

$$F = m\ddot{x} \quad (3)$$

with $m = \sigma A_0$, A_0 being the area of the flake and $\sigma = 4.6508 \text{ amu}/\text{\AA}^2$ the mass density of graphene. This analytical model will be used to extrapolate the motion patterns of graphene predicted by the MD simulation to understand experimental observations.

As a first test of the model, we consider the dependence of the maximum velocity of the flake with the mismatch ratio, x , shown in Figure 2(a). At larger mismatch, the flake is farther from its equilibrium position, so the maximum velocity should be greater. MD simulations of flakes of different sizes give nearly identical maximum velocities for a given mismatch ratio. Since the model potential energy is linearly proportional to offset ratio, $E \propto x$, the model predicts a square-root relation between maximum velocity and mismatch that is in good agreement with the MD results ($E = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 \propto x$). We also analyze the variation of lateral force with offset during one oscillation period predicted by MD simulation and the model in Figure 2(b) and (c), respectively. Similar results from DFT are shown in the supporting information, Figure S-5. The MD simulation and model (with appropriately chosen friction) give qualitatively similar results, again demonstrating that the simple model includes the forces necessary to describe the oscillatory motion of bilayer graphene.

In the MD simulations, the rate at which oscillatory motion decays is determined by the roughness of the graphene flakes (R_q). The analytical model decay rate is determined by the magnitude of the parameter c , which is the multiplicative prefactor of the friction term. The effects of R_q or c on the trajectory of the graphene flake are illustrated in Figure 3, where these parameters are varied such that the oscillatory motion patterns transition from very low damping (a and b), to moderately damped (c and d), and finally to highly damped (f). The consistency of the MD simulation and analytical model predictions in (a) through (d) further validate the analytical approach we have presented. Consequently, we can now apply that model to make predictions about larger-scale systems that are not accessible at the atomic-scale of the MD simulation. This enables direct comparison of the model results to the previously-reported experimental data shown in Figure 3(e) [2]. In Figure 3(f), the magnitude of c is fit such that the motion predicted by the analytical model closely resembles that of the experiment.

Friction between sliding surfaces is well-known to be a function of the roughness of those surfaces. The MD simulations describe the oscillatory behavior of graphene with variable roughness, thereby providing a means of exploring the connection between

Figure 2. (a) Increase of maximum (initial) flake velocity with mismatch ratio predicted by the analytical model and by MD simulations of perfectly flat graphene having three different sizes. Variation of lateral force with offset position for 100 Å square graphene with an initial offset of 70 Å predicted by (b) an MD simulation of rough graphene ($R_q=0.2$ Å) and (c) the corresponding analytical model ($c=0.01$ eV \times ps/Å²).

roughness and damping. The magnitude of the maximum offset position decreases exponentially over time ($L_0 \exp(-\lambda t)$). The decay rate (λ in the preceding equation) can be calculated from results such as those in Figure 3(a). Figure 4 shows the variation of this decay rate with R_q . Although the range of roughnesses accessible to the simulation is rather small, the relationship between roughness and decay rate appears to be approximately linear.

In order to progress beyond the time and size scales accessible to MD, and directly compare with experiment, we turn to the analytical model. The decay rate predicted by the model also shows a linear dependence on the friction constant c , as shown in Figure 4. The experimental data in Figure 3(e) can be approximated by the model with constants ranging from $c=0.19$ to 0.25 eV \times ps/Å². The resulting predictions correspond to decay rates from 0.015 to 0.023 ps⁻¹; this range is identified on Figure 4 as the shaded region. The size-scale limitations of MD preclude modeling surfaces with large roughness. However, linear extrapolation of the MD data to this range of decay rates reveals that they correspond to roughnesses between 2.75 and 4.2 Å, which is consistent with the roughness expected for graphene on a silicon dioxide substrate [12, 13].

Based on the linear relationships between decay rate and R_q and between decay rate at c , we infer there is a linear relationship between roughness and the friction

Figure 3. Decaying oscillatory motion of laterally-offset graphene. Low damping: (a) MD simulation with $R_q=0.2 \text{ \AA}$ and (b) analytical model with $c=0.01 \text{ eV}\times\text{ps}/\text{\AA}^2$, both for 100 \AA square graphene with an initial offset of 30 \AA . Moderate damping: (c) MD simulation with $R_q=0.44 \text{ \AA}$ and (d) analytical model with $c=0.04 \text{ eV}\times\text{ps}/\text{\AA}^2$, both for 100 \AA square graphene with an initial offset of 30 \AA . High damping: (e) experimental measurements from Ref. [2] and (f) the analytical model with $c=0.25 \text{ eV}\times\text{ps}/\text{\AA}^2$, both for $3 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ square graphene with initial offset 70 \AA .

constant. This leads to the expression $c=0.068(\text{eV}\times\text{ps}/\text{\AA}) \times R_q$ which provides a means of estimating the model friction constant for a given roughness. Therefore, for graphene of any roughness, the model presented here can be used to predict the corresponding oscillatory or self-retraction motion, bridging the gap between DFT and MD and experiment.

4. Conclusion

In summary, we have presented a multiscale approach utilizing density-functional theory, molecular dynamics simulation, and a reduced-order one-dimensional model to relate the experimental self-retraction behavior of graphene flakes to their surface roughness. Our DFT results provided accurate static energies, while the MD simulations predicted frictional sliding at the atomic level for variable roughness interfaces. The one-dimensional model was used to extrapolate MD results to the experimental time and size

Figure 4. Decay rate increasing with roughness from MD (lower x-axis) and with the magnitude of friction c from the analytical model (upper x-axis); the dashed line represents a linear fit to both data sets. The lower shaded region identifies the range of roughnesses and corresponding decay rates accessible to an MD simulation while the upper shaded region represents the range of c values and corresponding decay rates for which the model predictions are comparable to the experimental data in Figure 3(e).

scales, quantitatively explaining the oscillatory motion of the graphene bilayer in terms of roughness. This work reveals atomic-scale mechanisms underlying the relationship between microscale motion and nanoscale roughness, and ultimately suggests a means of prescribing the oscillation or self-retraction of bilayer graphene by tuning its substrate-dependent roughness.

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